

**PRIVATE COLLECTIONS IN THE HOLDINGS OF THE “A.S. PUSHKIN”
HOUSE-MUSEUM IN CHIȘINĂU**
Colecții private din fondurile Casei-muzeu „A.S. Pușkin” din Chișinău

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Summary. In the modern world, a museum is a place where numerous objects of cultural or historical significance are preserved, studied, and displayed. Regardless of its size, at the heart of any museum lies a collection, and behind every collection stands an enthusiast – a researcher, an antiquities and art lover, a seeker of adventures and artifacts, or simply a curious individual. Today, much is said about a country’s “cultural heritage,” which also encompasses the preservation of museum exhibits, each with its own unique story of how it came to be part of the museum’s holdings. Understanding the origins of these collections is a crucial task for any contemporary museum, as only in this way can the transfer of valuable objects between institutions be transparent, secure, and open to further scholarly inquiry.

This article examines the objects currently held in the collections of the “A.S. Pushkin” House-Museum that previously belonged to several notable private collections. Of interest are not only the scale and value of these collections but also the remarkable and multifaceted personalities of the collectors themselves, as well as the high level of professionalism they demonstrated in their respective fields. Of particular significance is the fact that a large part of their collections was transferred to museum holdings rather than scattered among private collections worldwide.

Among these individuals are the renowned orientalist and expert on Russian avant-garde art Igor Sanovich, the Doctor of Historical Sciences and archaeologist Igor Khlopin, and the engineer-designer, shipbuilder, collector, and numismatist Viktor Ashik.

Key words: “A.S. Pushkin” House-Museum, bookplate, Chișinău, collection, collector, museum, history, ex-libris

In modern society, it is important to recognize the significance of both national and global cultural heritage. Knowledge and understanding of the value of history and culture, along with adherence to international standards for the preservation of museum exhibits, are key aspects in fostering a respectful attitude toward cultural assets. Legal and ethical regulation of private and public collections is particularly relevant in the context of preventing the loss and illegal circulation of works of art.

The purpose of this article is to demonstrate that collecting is not only the process of gathering and preserving valuable items, but also a meaningful cultural mission. It involves systematization, research, and the transmission of cultural heritage to future generations, contributing to its preservation and promotion.

The topic of private collecting in the Republic of Moldova remains underexplored. There are no specialized communities or publications dedicated to this phenomenon in the country, nor are there systematic studies of national heritage in the context of collecting. This

work draws attention to the insufficient popularization and study of collecting practices, as well as to the need for unified principles of storage and transparency in the transfer of cultural property from one owner to another – principles that would ensure their preservation and accessibility to a wide audience.

The desire to preserve historical memory and establish a connection with the past has been inherent to humanity since ancient times. Even in prehistoric societies, there were sacred places, caves with rock art, and ritual collections, because “the impulse to preserve is a fundamental law that existed even before humankind appeared”.¹

The first Mouseion, founded by Ptolemy I in Alexandria around 290 BCE, was an educational institution that included living quarters, dining halls, reading rooms, botanical and zoological gardens, an observatory, and a library. Precursors of the modern museum can be seen in treasuries, particularly those within temples, where objects – often considered sacred – were preserved and displayed. In the 16th century, key elements of future museum institutions began to take shape in collecting practices: well-developed concepts, inventory systems, and exhibitions organized according to specific curatorial ideas.

Thus, the development of museums and the foundations of modern museology were significantly influenced by the practice of collecting, which began to spread during the Renaissance.²

The next major stage in the development of collecting and the emergence of a professional approach to creating collections was the establishment of the first public museums. In 1753, the British Museum opened in London. Its permanent exhibition was based on three private collections donated to the museum – featuring taxidermied animals, artifacts from island cultures, religious manuscripts, and secular books.

Initially, the museum sought to impress and astonish visitors, and the collections were displayed without strict classification. The position of curator was introduced to oversee the organization of exhibitions. Interestingly, in English, the verb to curate means “to select,” emphasizing the curator’s role in sourcing and choosing artifacts to enhance the collection.

One of the first Italian collectors to take a deliberate approach to acquiring items was Petrarch, who formed a significant collection of coins and books and laid the foundation for the studiolo – rooms specially designated for storing collections. In the 15th century, Isabella d’Este of the Gonzaga family developed this principle further, focusing on painting and commissioning works from leading masters such as Giovanni Bellini and Leonardo da Vinci.

In the 16th century, the culture of the studiolo spread to Central Europe, evolving into the concept of Cabinets of Curiosities (Cabinet of Curiosities in the UK and Wunderkammer in the German principalities). Gradually, collectors moved from chaotic accumulation to the creation of specialized thematic collections. Flanders became a leader in producing inlaid cabinets, and artisans from Antwerp and Amsterdam served collectors across Europe. During this period, the first catalog of a private collection was compiled by David Teniers the Younger, court curator of the Habsburg collection.³

¹ The Museum as a Cultural Phenomenon. Vladimir Regional Scientific Library, 2000–2025. URL: <https://library.vladimir.ru/news/muzej-kak-fenomen-kultury.html> (accessed 27.01.2025).

² Museum. Great Russian Encyclopedia, 2014–2017. URL: <https://old.bigenc.ru/education/text/2236403> (accessed 28.01.2025).

³ D. Belkevich, Investment in Art: A Brief History of Collecting from the Venetian Republic to the 20th Century. // ARTinvestment, 2025. URL: https://artinvestment.ru/invest/collector/20200212_collecting_story.html (accessed 25.01.2025).

During the Age of Enlightenment, museums acquired educational and moral significance, becoming centers of scientific inquiry and the dissemination of knowledge. Their creation was initiated by scholars, educators, and enlightened monarchs who used museums to explore the world and educate society.⁴

The 19th century can be described as a period of collecting enthusiasm, when the fashion for gathering antiques was actively developing across Europe and the United Kingdom. The term antique first appeared in the 18th century to denote an object that had lost its original practical function and become a symbol of a bygone era.

In Russia, collecting gained momentum under Peter I, who gathered rare and unusual items during his travels – objects that would later form the foundation of the *Kunstkamera*. By the early 19th century, collecting became more widespread: its themes expanded, as did the social circle of collectors. Many private collections became the basis for museum holdings. Collectors began to systematize their collections, compile catalogues, and open them to the public. For instance, the collection of A. D. Chertkov formed the foundation of the book collection of the Historical Museum, while the collection of N. N. Demidov contributed to the Natural History Museum of Moscow University.⁵

At the beginning of the 20th century, Russian collecting, developed within the broader European context, gained international recognition. However, this period of stability came to an end. The world war, the revolutions of 1917, and the era of war communism led to the loss of many collections. Some were taken abroad, while others were nationalized or sold off.

Palaces and estates were transferred to the state and turned into museums, and former owners often voluntarily donated valuables to protect them from looting. By the end of the 1920s, the official antiques market had disappeared, and underground art trading gradually declined. Yet even under such dramatic circumstances – including repression and war – private collecting continued to exist.⁶

Collecting in Bessarabia developed according to the same principles as in other parts of Europe. In the 19th century, not only aristocrats but also wealthy, educated individuals engaged in collecting. However, political upheavals led to the loss of most collections: rare items were either taken abroad or transferred to museums, while those that remained in private hands became fragmented and often lost their connection to their previous owners.

With the rise of Soviet power, private collections, like museums, were nationalized. The state eliminated the institution of private property. Nevertheless, even in the USSR, there existed an underground art market and private collectors who preserved the traditions of collecting despite prohibitions and state control.

There were no private enterprises, theaters, clinics, restaurants, etc., in the Soviet Union. As for museums, the Soviet authorities nationalized them at the very beginning of their rule. The same fate befell private collections after the revolution. Later, the state destroyed the

⁴ V.P. Gritskevich, *The History of Museology in the World (until the end of the 18th century)*. [Online] Studfiles, 2003. URL: <https://studfile.net/preview/5439611/page:7/> (accessed 25.01.2025).

⁵ How Private Collecting Developed in Russia. Part I. First Gallery G1, 2016. URL: <https://g1.gallery/ru/feed/articles/2016/08/15/the-history-of-private-art-collecting-in-russia-1-268/> (accessed 25.01.2025).

⁶ How Private Collecting Developed in Russia. Part I. First Gallery G1, 2016. URL: <https://g1.gallery/ru/feed/articles/2016/08/15/the-history-of-private-art-collecting-in-russia-1-268/> (accessed 25.01.2025).

very concept of private property. Nonetheless, an underground art market took shape, and private collectors did exist in the Soviet Union.⁷

“Who were these collectors of the Soviet era? Where did they come from in a country where all private property was banned or subject to immediate ‘confiscation’? Where even the word ‘collector’ rhymed, in the public consciousness, with derogatory terms like ‘speculator,’ ‘currency trader,’ ‘black marketeer’? Not the Morozovs, not the Tretyakovs, but law-abiding Soviet citizens living from one paycheck to the next. How did they suddenly acquire such fabulous luxury amid the dreary Soviet reality and its seemingly eternal norms?”

“A new stratum of collectors emerged from the party elite and the creative intelligentsia, who were granted unofficial permission by the state to acquire works of art. Art historian Inna Pulikova names several prominent collectors of the Soviet period. Among them were: writer Alexei Tolstoy, singer Lidia Ruslanova, ballerina Ekaterina Geltser, artist Pavel Korin, actors Maria Mironova and Alexander Menaker, writer Vladimir Soloukhin, and artist Ilya Glazunov.”

“Each of these collections deserves a separate exhibition, and the stories of their formation – along with even brief biographical details about their owners – reveal how much history and emotion intertwined in these small apartment spaces.”⁸

The A.S. Pushkin House Museum in Chișinău was established in 1948, initially occupying only a few small rooms, including an exhibition space and storage area. Until the early 1970s, the museum’s main collection was composed primarily of thematic books, photographs, photodocuments, and only occasionally domestic objects, along with commissioned paintings and graphic works created specifically for the thematic exhibition. Most of the items were donations.

Since 1983, when the museum’s territory and exhibition space were significantly expanded, a complete renovation was carried out, and the museum was designated as a site of “All-Union significance.” Funding began to be allocated for acquiring exhibits in accordance with the updated museum’s status. This opened broad opportunities for the museum to expand its reserves from a variety of sources. These sources were fairly standard for any Soviet museum: exchange funds from libraries, archives, and other museums; state-run antique shops; and, of course, private collections. However, even when working with private individuals, all purchases of museum exhibits had to be conducted through special state procurement commissions.

While connections with state institutions were more or less established, contacting private collectors was usually only possible through personal recommendations or acquaintances. In this respect, the A.S. Pushkin House Museum in Chișinău was extremely fortunate – several collectors from Leningrad and Moscow not only welcomed the delegation of researchers from Chișinău but also worked fruitfully for several years on selecting and searching for exhibits not only related to Pushkin but also covering the entire historical period from the late 18th to the late 19th centuries.

“...I vividly remember the sound of dried-out parquet creaking, the scent of wood polished with wax, mixed with something that resembled valerian drops or Valocordin – something heart-related, in any case. And those paintings on the walls, pressed tightly against

⁷ S. Nikolaevich, *Trophies and Fates. On the Exhibition ‘Art Hunters’ at the Museum of Russian Impressionism*. Snob, 14.05.2011. URL: <https://snob.ru/entry/206892/> (accessed 21.08.2024).

⁸ S. Nikolaevich, *Trophies and Fates. On the Exhibition ‘Art Hunters’ at the Museum of Russian Impressionism*. Snob, 14.05.2011. URL: <https://snob.ru/entry/206892/> (accessed 21.08.2024).

one another: frame to frame, edge to edge, so that you couldn't even see the wallpaper behind them. At first, you couldn't even make out what the paintings depicted. It was like a wild, desperate explosion of color, an endless, uninterrupted fireworks display under which you were expected to hold a polite social conversation – trying your best not to glance around too much, so as not to look completely provincial. These were the kinds of homes they had, the kinds of collections they kept".⁹

These are memories from the article “Trophies and Fates. On the exhibition ‘Art Hunters’ at the Museum of Russian Impressionism”, dedicated to Soviet collectors, particularly one of the most well-known among them – Igor Sanovich. (Figs. 1-2) Igor Grigoryevich Sanovich (November 4, 1923, Moscow – March 24, 2010, Moscow) was a Soviet and Russian orientalist, scholar of Iran (Persia), and collector of Russian avant-garde and fine art.

Fig. 1. Igor Sanovich. Photographic portrait <https://homsk.com/margo/ohotniki-za-iskusstvom-chto-i-kak-sobirali-sovetskie-kollekcionery>

Fig. 2. Artist V.G. Weisberg, Double Portrait (Anya and Igor. Portrait of a Samurai), 1961. <https://pro100-mica.livejournal.com/1120734.html>

Sanovich's passion for art began in his youth. Over time, he became recognized as an outstanding collector – one of the “old school” connoisseurs, considered a legend in Russian collecting circles. According to contemporaries, he was among the last collectors guided solely by intuition and artistic instinct, rather than profit: “Over five decades of collecting, Sanovich managed to create a private collection comparable to a museum of world artistic culture.”¹⁰

“He assembled a phenomenal collection – or rather, several collections: Russian icons and Western European primitives, paintings and drawings of all times and nations, Persian, Western European, and Old Russian miniatures, porcelain, beadwork. And also: Judaica, Chinese and Persian small sculpture, Japanese prints and netsuke, and artifacts from Scythian, Alanic, and Greek settlements...” – recalled Alexander Kronik.¹¹

In 2014, the Pushkin State Museum of Fine Arts (Department of Private Collections) held an exhibition dedicated to collectors – “Apartment-Museum.” Five Moscow collections were selected for the exhibition, including the collection of Igor Sanovich, to which three halls were devoted.

⁹ S. Nikolaevich. Trophies and Fates. On the exhibition “Art Hunters” at the Museum of Russian Impressionism. Snob, 14.05.2011. URL: <https://snob.ru/entry/206892/> (accessed 21.08.2024).

¹⁰ The Passing of Collector I.G. Sanovich. // ARTinvestment.ru: Portal on the Art Market. URL: https://artinvestment.ru/invest/painters/20100325__sanovich.html (accessed 17.12.2024)

¹¹ The Passing of Collector I.G. Sanovich. // ARTinvestment.ru: Portal on the Art Market. URL: https://artinvestment.ru/invest/painters/20100325__sanovich.html (accessed 17.12.2024)

Among the holdings of the A.S. Pushkin House-Museum, donated by collector Igor Sanovich, there are several valuable items. However, the most significant of them is considered to be the item with inventory number 11938 – the “Hunting” vase from the 18th century, acquired in 1989. According to the transfer documents, this rare piece is part of a unique set of five elements created in 1741 at the Meissen Manufactory as a gift for French King Louis XV.

The vases “Fire,” “Water,” “Earth,” and “Air” – monumental allegories of the four elements – remain among the most sought-after creations of Meissen porcelain art. In 1741, Saxon Elector Frederick Augustus II commissioned sculptor and artist Johann Joachim Kändler to create this luxurious set. The composition, symbolizing the harmony of the elements, was presented to Louis XV as a sign of the strong allied relations between Saxony and France.

Originally, the ensemble consisted of five pieces. The central vase, 85 cm tall, was the largest created in the 18th century and was decorated with a portrait of Louis XV. Surrounding it were two lidded vases – allegories of “Fire and War” and “Earth and Hunting.”

In Kändler’s description, “Earth” is depicted as a vase adorned with hunting scenes: in relief, a deer, roe deer, hounds are shown, and the composition is crowned by the figure of the goddess Diana among forest landscapes.¹²

Experts from the Hermitage, referring to the magazine “Starye Gody” (Old Years, May 1911), note that archival materials include a photograph of two vases from this ensemble – “Earth” and “Fire.” However, in current Hermitage sources, only “Fire” is mentioned.¹³

Thus, the question remains open: is the vase from Chișinău the very one once housed in the pre-revolutionary Hermitage, or has another rare specimen of the legendary collection survived in Moldova... (Figs. 3-5).

Igor Nikolaevich Khlopin (June 7, 1930, Leningrad – December 7, 1994, St. Petersburg) was a Soviet and Russian archaeologist, Doctor of Historical Sciences (1984), and a special-

Fig. 3. Vase “Earth” (“Hunting”), 1741. Meissen, Germany

Fig. 4. Vase “Earth” (“Hunting”), 1741. Meissen, Germany. A. Pushkin House-Museum/ Grabovscaia M.

Fig. 5. Photo from the magazine Starye Gody (Old Years), May, 1911. A. Pushkin House-Museum

¹² Vase-Allegory “Earth and Hunting.” Catalog, 2022. URL: <https://art-salon.eu/ru/catalog/vaza-allegoriya-zemlya-i-ohota> (Accessed: 27.08.2024).

¹³ S. Troynitsky, Gallery of Porcelain of the Imperial Hermitage. Starye Gody (Old Years), May 1911, pp. 24-26.

list in the ancient history and archaeology of Central Asia. During World War II, the Khlopin family was evacuated to Samarkand, where, still a schoolboy, he first encountered the rich historical and cultural heritage of the East – an experience that shaped his future academic interests. After returning to Leningrad, he entered the Department of Archaeology at the Faculty of History of Leningrad State University (LGU). Khlopin actively pursued academic research and participated in numerous archaeological expeditions. In 1968, he headed the Sumbar Archaeological Expedition, which resulted in the monograph “Southwestern Turkmenistan in the Late Bronze Age” (1983). In the 1980s, he turned his attention to the study of Old Russian architecture, thereby expanding the scope of his scholarly interests. (Fig. 6)

In addition to archaeology, he studied a wide range of subjects: the origins of carpet weaving, the semantics of pottery ornamentation, funerary rites, and the roots of Zoroastrianism. He authored about 170 scientific publications, including nine monographs.¹⁴

Exhibits from his collection first appeared in the Chișinău museum in 1983. These included household items, applied art, books, and furniture. In 1986, the museum acquired from him an incredible collection of 1,700 bookplates (ex libris), including heraldic and artistic ones – some of which exist in only a few copies worldwide. Most notably, it includes a truly unique item: a 15th-century ex libris – which, according to the latest confirmed data, is dated to the year 1475. (Fig. 7)

The ex libris discovered in an old book at the Carthusian Monastery of Buxheim (Swabia) is considered the oldest known bookplate. Copies of it have been found in a number of old manuscripts bound in wooden covers, which were donated to the monastery by Hilprand Brandenburg. The bookplate image depicts an angel with outspread wings holding a shield that features a bull with a ring in its nose. The authenticity of the bookplate is confirmed by handwritten notes found in books bearing this mark, which describe Brandenburg’s gift in

Fig. 6. Igor Khlopin. Photographic portrait, <https://arheologija.ru/pamyati-igorya-nikolaevicha-hlopina-1930-1994/>

Fig. 7. Hilprand Brandenburg’s ex libris, ca. 1475. A. Pushkin House-Museum/ Grabovscaia M.

¹⁴ Igor Khlopin: Tireless Researcher of the Antiquities of Southern Turkmenistan [Online]URL: <https://turkmenistan.gov.tm/ru/post/53293/igor-hlopin-neutomimyj-issledovatel-drevnostej-yuzhno-go-turkmenistana> (Accessed: 10.12.2024).

detail. In a copy of *Quæstiones super primo libro Sententiarum* by Saint Bonaventure, there is a dedicatory inscription that translates as: “This book belongs to the Carthusian Monastery of Buxheim, near Memmingen, and was donated by Hilprand Brandenburg of Biberach.”¹⁵

Equally rare is the *ex libris* of Antiochus Kantemir, created around 1735–38 in France. According to Lukomsky, it is considered an “*incunabulum*” of Russian bookplates (a term used for all bookplates made before 1750).¹⁶ For a long time, this bookplate did not “resurface” in any known bookplate collections, and it was first mentioned in Russia only in 1911. Today, the collection of bookplates held by the A.S. Pushkin House-Museum in Chisinau includes over 15,000 items and is the largest collection of bookplates in Moldova. It is undoubtedly a true cultural treasure and heritage of the country.

Viktor Ashik (1905 – September 3, 1985, Leningrad) – engineer-designer, shipbuilder, collector, numismatist, and polymath, possessed encyclopedic knowledge and was fluent in almost all European languages, both modern and ancient. (Fig. 9)

Fig. 8. Antiochus Kantemir's *ex libris*, ca. 1735. A. Pushkin House-Museum/ Grabovscaia M.

Fig. 9. V.V. Ashik in his study. Photograph

<https://yarwiki.ru/article/2075/viktor-ashik-i-ego-kollekciya>

Viktor Vladimirovich Ashik was the USSR's foremost collector of Russian commemorative medals and tokens, with a collection of over 4,000 items. The collection was originally started by his grandfather and then expanded by his father – a renowned Russian numismatist and author of the book *Monuments and Medals Commemorating the Military Feats of the Russian Army in the Wars of 1812–1814*.

After his father's death, Viktor Vladimirovich managed to double the number of items in this extraordinary collection. By the 1980s, the Ashik collection included over 22,000 items, among them 14,000 works of painting, graphics, numismatics, decorative and applied arts, and furniture. After his death, Ashik's collection was acquired by the Yaroslavl Art Museum, “doubling its holdings and significantly elevating the quality of its classical museum sections in Russian painting, graphics, and decorative arts. A new numismatics department was also created.”¹⁷

¹⁵ *Bookplates for Beginners* by Alfred Fowler – copyright 1921. [Online] *Ex Libris Art*, 2011–2025. URL: <https://www.exlibris-art.com/the-origins-of-ex-libris/> (accessed: 04.01.2025).

¹⁶ *Proceedings of the Leningrad Society of Ex Libris Enthusiasts*, Vol. II–III, 1924.

¹⁷ *Viktor Ashik and His Collection* // *Yarwiki* (Yarwiki.ru). URL: <https://yarwiki.ru/article/2075/viktor-ashik-i-ego-kollekciya> (accessed: 13.12.2024).

Fig. 10. C. Bossoli, Bakhchisarai. The Khan's Palace, 1842

At the A.S. Pushkin House-Museum, one of the prized pieces from the Ashik collection is a beautiful watercolor by Carlo Bossoli titled Bakhchisarai, painted in 1842. (Fig. 10, 11)

Carlo Bossoli (December 6, 1815, Lugano, Switzerland – August 1, 1884, Turin, Italy) was a painter of Italian and Swiss origin, known for his work in landscape, maritime, and battle painting, and also as a traveler. His youth was spent in the southern part of the Russian Empire – in Odessa and Crimea – where he was under the patronage of Count Mikhail Vorontsov, the governor of Novorossiia and Bessarabia.

Fig. 11. C. Bossoli, Bakhchisarai. The Khan's Palace, 1842, detail with artist's signature. A. Pushkin House-Museum/ Grabovscaia M.

In 1840, Bossoli visited Crimea and spent two years in Alupka, at the Vorontsov estate. During this time, he traveled extensively across the peninsula and created over 70 landscapes.

This watercolor was purchased directly from Viktor Ashik in 1984, shortly before his death. It is now carefully preserved in the museum's collections and for many years was one of the central exhibits of the museum's permanent display. It remains one of the main treasures of the museum's collection.

In the study of collecting, debates continue about the reliability of preservation in private versus public collections, with a distinction made between "gathering" and "collecting." The key difference lies in the presence of a conscious goal: collecting includes not only the accumulation but also the systematization, study, and preservation of cultural values. Unlike simple gathering, collecting contributes to the spread of artistic awareness and cultural

norms.¹⁸ In this context, we must not forget the tragic fate that befell the historical museum of Ivan Suruchanu. “The Museum of Antiquities of the Scythian Pontus in Chisinau was established by antiquities collector, archaeologist, and expert in ancient history Ivan Kasyanovich Suruchanu. He began forming his museum in the 1870s.”¹⁹ By 1897, the collection contained 90,443 items, making it one of the largest museum institutions in the southern Russian Empire.

Suruchanu's sudden death in November 1897 left his work on systematizing the collection and implementing preservation measures unfinished. A full catalog of the collection was never compiled. In the absence of specialists to continue the work or funds to acquire the collection in its entirety, over the following years it was sold off piece by piece and was plundered during 1917. This story vividly illustrates how the treasures of a once-rich collection can essentially vanish from a country's cultural space without protection.

Preservation and display are two fundamental responsibilities of any owner of a unique collection. Museums play a key role in this process, ensuring not only the safety of artifacts but also their accessibility to the public. Through exhibitions, educational programs, and scholarly research, they promote the dissemination and study of cultural heritage.

As for private collections, history has shown that they often become the only means of saving artworks during times of social upheaval. Yet their fate remains uncertain: private collections frequently dissolve, and artworks are scattered among various owners. Meanwhile, museums guarantee the long-term preservation of artifacts and ensure they remain accessible to the wider public.

It is also impossible to ignore the legal and ethical issues of cultural property storage. State regulations and standardized storage rules provide a more reliable mechanism for protecting cultural heritage than the subjective decisions of private owners. In this regard, museum curation appears to be the most sustainable and enduring form of preserving art and historical relics.

¹⁸ E.A. Makarova, *Collecting as a Socio-Cultural Institution*. 169 pages. Dissertation Electronic Library, 2022. URL: <https://www.dissercat.com/content/kolleksionirovanie-kak-sotsiokulturnyi-institut> (accessed: 25.02.2025).

¹⁹ A. Kostenko, *The 'Lost Collection' of Ivan Suruchan in the Kherson Regional Museum of Local Lore*, in: *Tyragegia, Series New*, vol. X [XXV], no. 1, 2016, pp. 345-356, p. 345.